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Research Article

**EMERGENCY BASED ULTRASOUND OF CLINICALLY
SUPPOSED ACUTE APPENDICITIS WITH LOW
FREQUENCY CURVILINEAR TRANSDUCER AND ITS
RELATION WITH SURGICAL OUTCOME**¹Dr Faria Afzal, ²Dr Junaid Afzal, ³Dr Ghulam Jamil¹JIANGXI University of Traditional Chinese Medicine, China²JIANGXI University of Traditional Chinese Medicine, China³I.K. Akhunbaev Kyrgyz State Medical Academy (Bishkek Kyrgyzstan)**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To determine the diagnostic accuracy of low frequency curvilinear transducer as an ancillary emergency tool for clinical suspects of acute appendicitis and its association with surgical outcome.

Material and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Radiology department Unit-II of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020. 89 cases (38 men, 51 women; age 12–70 years, mean age 37 years) of clinically suspected acute appendicitis were included. The clinical classification is based on the Alvarado score. Transabdominal ultrasound was performed using a 3.5 MHz low-frequency curvilinear transducer with the graduated compression technique, followed by a 7.5 MHz high-frequency linear transducer. All cases underwent appendectomy. The inflammation of the sample was assessed on the basis of histopathology.

Results: Out of 89 patients, 71 were typical and 18 atypical clinical signs and symptoms of acute appendicitis. On ultrasound, the appendix was visualized in 73 cases (82%) with a low-frequency transducer, compared to 78 cases (87.6%) with a high-frequency transducer. The sensitivity and specificity of the preoperative ultrasound examination were approximately 68.0% and 88.0%, respectively. It was also found that the link between ultrasound and histopathological diagnostic evidence is statistically significant ($p = 0.000$).

Conclusion: The negative appendix rate can be significantly reduced by thorough ultrasound examination using a low-frequency transducer, which is helpful in clinical evaluation.

Key words: acute appendicitis, ultrasound, transducer, sensitivity, specificity

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute appendicitis is one of the most common clinical units in the emergency department requiring surgical intervention. Patients with the usual clinical symptoms of acute appendicitis undergo immediate surgery. In addition to significantly improving imaging technology, radiological imaging is usually reserved for unusual or unclear cases. Even after spiral computed tomography (CT) and color Doppler emergence, grayscale ultrasound (US) is still the initial imaging method in patients suspected of having appendicitis. Ultrasound can quickly help distinguish between appendicitis patients needing a CT scan or immediate surgery. In recent years, emphasis has been placed on the visualization of a normal appendix. Being able to make a differential diagnosis is important to both clinicians and emergency radiologists as many conditions can mimic the clinical symptoms of acute appendicitis including gallbladder disease, acute pyelonephritis, urolithiasis, infectious / inflammatory cecum / ascending colon and abnormal diseases such as complicated ovarian cysts, hemorrhage, and torsion. The availability of advanced imaging methods, including computed tomography and color Doppler, is a problem that has not yet been resolved in many emergency departments of third-degree hospitals in our country. However, US gray scale is only available in most settings with only a single low-frequency curvilinear transducer. Taking this fact into account, we have set ourselves the goal of determining the diagnostic accuracy of a low-frequency curvilinear transducer as an emergency tool in the case of suspected acute appendicitis and its correlation with the result of surgery.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Radiology department Unit-II of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020. 89 cases (38 men, 51 women; age range 12-70 years, mean age 37 years) suspected of having acute appendicitis clinically in the emergency department were included. Patients were classified as typical or atypical for

appendicitis with acute inflammation using the Alvarado scale. Transabdominal ultrasound was performed by one radiologist using the Toshiba Nemio XG ultrasound machine with a low frequency 3.5 MHz curvilinear transducer. The technique consisted of gradual pressure with even pressure on the transducer on the lower right quadrant to displace normal and gas-filled intestinal loops from sight or to compress between the muscles of the abdominal wall 5. The abnormal or occluded appendix remained incompressible and was optimally imaged. The gentle maintenance of pressure allowed long-term evaluation of a given area of interest even in the most uncomfortable and reluctant patients with peritoneal irritation. The transverse, sagittal and oblique planes from the tip of the liver to the edge of the pelvis were visualized. Inflammatory changes in the peritoneal fat and the appendix were carefully monitored. After initial scanning, a 7.5 MHz linear HF transducer was used to compare and demonstrate more detailed sonographic characteristics. Appendicolith appeared as bright, echogenic outbreaks with a dense rear acoustic shadow. In the case of the perforated appendix, the widening of the lumen was no longer visualized, but the peritoneal fluid and inflammatory changes in the peritoneal adipose tissue were visible. In a few cases, sympathetic thickening of the adjacent terminal ileum and ascending colon has also been demonstrated. All cases were subjected to surgical appendectomy, and the excerpt was sent for histopathological examination for evaluation of inflammatory changes. For statistical analysis, frequencies and percentages of categorical variables were measured and compared. In addition, the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive values and negative predictive values were calculated. The association of histopathological diagnosis with ultrasonography was measured with the Fisher's exact test at a significance level of 5%.

RESULTS:

Of the 89 patients, 83 had typical clinical signs and signs indicative of acute appendicitis. However, 24 patients reported atypically (Table 1).

Table-1: Distribution of age and gender according to the clinical presentation in the sample population.

Age Group (Yrs)	Clinical Presentation			
	Male	Female	Male	Female
≤10	2	3	1	-
11-20	9	14	2	5
21-30	13	17	3	4
31-40	6	4	1	1
>40	1	2	-	1
Total	31	40	7	11

It found that more patients fell in the 2nd to 4th decade of life. Women dominated in the atypical clinical picture. In the transabdominal ultrasound examination, the appendix was visualized in 73 cases (82%) using a

low-frequency curvilinear transducer. We compared this driver with a high frequency linear driver. For comparison, there was only a slight increase in the visualization of the appendix, i.e. 78 cases (87.6%). Table 2 compares the sensitivity and specificity of the low-frequency curvilinear transducer with the linear high-frequency (adopted as the gold standard), which explains that the low-frequency sensitivity is around 94.0% and the specificity is 100%. Hence curvilinear low frequency can also give almost the same efficient visualization of the appendix as with a high frequency transducer.

Table-2: Sensitivity and specificity measures for visualization of appendix using low and high frequency transducers (n=89)

Appendiceal Imaging		Linear high frequency 7.5 MHz	
		Visualized	Non-visualized
Curvilinear low frequency 3.5 MHz	Visualized	73	0
	Non-Visualized	5	11

The appendix visualized by a low-frequency curvilinear transducer was then divided into appendicitis with normal morphology, appendicitis with acute inflammation or perforated appendix. Most of the patients with clinical suspicion fell into the acute inflammation category (Table 3).

Table-3: Sonographic categorization of appendix by low frequency transducer in typical and atypical cases.

Clinical presentation	Sonographic features of appendiceal imaging with low frequency curvilinear transducer			
	Appendix not visualized	Normal morphology of appendix	Inflamed appendix	Perforated appendix
Typical (n=71)	10	11	46	4
Atypical (n=18)	6	3	8	1

There were approximately 17 cases that turned negative for any histological evidence of inflammation suggesting a 19.1% negative appendix rate. Table 4 compares the results of pre-operative ultrasound diagnostics with the histopathological symptoms of appendicitis (gold standard). The results showed that the sensitivity and specificity of ultrasound diagnostics to the gold standard are 68.0% and 88.0%, respectively, indicating that there is an approximately 68.0% chance of correctly classifying true positive appendages by ultrasound with respect to histopathological evidence. Likewise, the accurate detection of true negative cases is around 88.0%. Moreover, using the Fisher's exact test, it was found that there was a significant relationship between the methods of detecting ultrasound and histopathology ($p = 0.000$). Hence, ultrasound diagnosis can also be a useful auxiliary tool in detecting appendicitis, given the sensitivity and specificity greater than 50.0%.

Table 4: Histopathology of surgically resected appendages and preoperative ultrasound association.

Histopathology of surgically resected appendices		Preoperative sonographic diagnosis	
		-ve scan (n=25)	+ve scan (n=25)
Gold Standard	-ve for inflammation	17	8
	+ve for inflammation	8	64

DISCUSSION:

High frequency linear probes are still widely used in the imaging of appendicitis. However, we found that in a large number of patients, the curvilinear low frequency driver performed equally well compared to the linear driver. Wide availability, as well as a larger field of view and greater penetration are the main advantages that make the curvilinear transducer more and more used by radiologists and sonologists. A particular benefit for obese patients is another aspect where it is difficult to adequately scan with a superficially

penetrating linear probe. We believe that the proper selection of the appendix head is a critical factor. Timely diagnosis of acute appendicitis is essential to minimize the morbidity that remains significant when perforation occurs. Current surgical procedures generally recommend a balance between negative laparotomy and the rate of perforation during surgery. Recent advances nowadays increasingly emphasize the role of medical imaging in appendicitis, in addition to the correlation of clinical and laboratory parameters. Ultrasound underdiagnosis of acute appendicitis is

common if the inflammation is localized only at the end of the appendix, leading to the false impression that the appendix is normal. These could be other problems. Related to the position of the appendix, which makes it difficult to judge, especially when it is inside the real pelvis and outside the caecum. Moreover, perforation of the appendix can lead to a decompression of the appendix so that the appendix itself is no longer visible. The overdiagnosis of appendicitis on ultrasound is mainly due to a misinterpretation of the terminal ileum as an appendix, which, unlike the appendix, exhibits frequent peristaltic activity and does not attach to the base of the cecum and is not blind. With the advent of spiral computed tomography and color Doppler ultrasound, inflammatory activity in the appendix and soft tissues around the appendix can be accurately detected. The contribution is most evident in the case of an ambiguous grayscale ultrasound. The choice of imaging method depends largely on institutional preferences and the knowledge available, although patient age, sex and body composition are important influencing factors. Ultrasound is still the first choice in most centers because it is fast, non-invasive, cost-effective, and requires no patient preparation or contrast media injection. Since the ultrasound examination does not include ionizing radiation and is perfect for imaging acute gynecological conditions, it is the recommended initial imaging examination in children, young women and pregnant women. CT is complementary to ultrasound and is recommended whenever the ultrasound results are suboptimal, indeterminate, or normal in patients with acute abdominal pain.

CONCLUSION:

The negative rate of appendicitis can be significantly reduced by thorough ultrasound using a linear low-frequency transducer. Ultrasound can play a role in appendicitis imaging to increase diagnostic accuracy and clinical evaluation to identify right lower quadrant pain as acute appendicitis, especially in inconclusive cases. Whether it should be performed in all patients with suspected acute appendicitis, or whether it should be reserved for atypical clinical signs, is still a matter of debate for clinicians prior to surgical decision making. We recommend pre-operative ultrasound as an inexpensive supportive tool for clinical evaluation in all suspects of acute appendicitis.

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